

PROBLEM OF ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY IN THE INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In the second half of the XX-early XXI centuries, theoretical approaches to the status of men and women in the system of international relations began to appear in the article, which rejected tradition. The fact that stereotypes of the "policy for men, and family and children – for women" lose their relevance in connection with the social changes that are manifested in practice, economic, political, social issues facing humanity, problems of ensuring peace, stability and equal security for all and that women are equally affected as men, in this matter, the recognition of human rights. At the same time, views on issues such as the fact that gender equality is considered an integral part of sustainable development are being discussed today, and research on gender equality, the development of evidence-based proposals and recommendations aimed at equalizing the social and political rights of men and women are of particular importance.*

Keywords: *reading, professional education, activity, mobility, academic mobility, logical structure, educational process, system, logical structure, transparency, professional mobility.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the second half of the twentieth century and the beginning of the twenty-first century, specific, tradition-rejecting theoretical approaches to the status of men and women began to emerge in the system of international relations. Now, due to social changes in practice, stereotypes such as "politics - for men, family and children - for women" are losing their relevance. The economic, political and social issues facing humanity, the problems of peace, stability and security apply equally to all. It is recognized around the world that women are equally involved in this issue as men. Today, the issue of gender equality is considered an integral part of sustainable development [1.p.111].

Naturally, the UN's 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development addresses the issue of gender equality in Goal 5, which states that "Gender equality is not only a fundamental human right, but also a necessary condition for a peaceful and sustainable life [7.p.p. 111-113]

Recognition of the issue of gender balance in the world as an important condition for sustainable social development, in turn, requires the priority of scientific research on this topic. In this regard, special attention is paid to research to ensure gender equality in the system of international relations and its integration into all spheres of society and state life, to improve the system of international institutions on gender issues. The Republic of Uzbekistan, acceding to many international instruments and recognizing the supremacy of international law, pays great attention to increasing the role of women in building the state and society on the issue of gender equality. The state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at implementing the principles

of equality and freedom, creating equal opportunities for women and men in accordance with the Constitution and the legal framework based on it.

"People's consent is, first of all, connected with the consent of mothers, women, ensuring their health and happiness is the main goal and criterion of all reforms ...". In this context, research on gender equality and the development of science-based proposals and recommendations aimed at equalizing the rights of men and women in the social and political spheres are of particular importance. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF 4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", Decree No. PF-5325 of February 2, 2018 "On measures to radically improve the activities in the field of support of women and strengthening the institution of the family", Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3751 of May 29, 2018; Decree No. PF-5938 of February 18, 2020 "On measures to improve the environment, further support the institution of the community and bring the system of work with families and women to a new level" and "Organization of the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support of the Republic of Uzbekistan Resolution No. PQ-4602 of February 18, 2020, In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 12, 2020 "On the parameters of the state order of admission to higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the 2020/2021 academic year" Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4235 of March 7, 2019 "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship" Law on the Protection of Women from Oppression and Violence. "Equal for men and women, Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 30, 2020 No 192 "On approval of regulations on gender and legal examination of regulations and their drafts", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 23, 2020 No 402 "On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for issuing recommendations to women to participate in the competition and the organization of their admission to higher education institutions on the basis of additional state grants", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the system of protection of women from oppression and violence" dated January 4, 2020 No 4, Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 20, 2019 "On employment of women, development of entrepreneurship among them Resolution No. 919 "On measures to further improve the system", a high-level meeting dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the IV World Conference on the Status of Women was held on October 1, 2019 at the UN Headquarters in New York. Minutes of the meeting of the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis. as well as the fact that the implementation of the tasks set out in other normative legal acts on the subject is directly in the interests of women [2], Resolution of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, N. SQ-297-IV dated 05/28/2021,

II. THE MAIN PART

The work of foreign authors on this topic can be divided into several groups. The first group - Z. Eisenstein, S. ; Bovuar, V. Brayson, R.Xof, B. Xuks, C. West, D. The theoretical and methodological foundations of gender research are reflected in the work of a group of scholars such as Zimmermann. Positive discrimination strategies in democracies and their impact on women's political representation P. Norris and J. Analyzed by Lovenduski. R. Moser, on the other hand, examines the impact of electoral systems on women's representation. The results of the study devoted to the study of the experience of the Scandinavian countries as an advanced model of

promoting political equality at the national level are reflected in the work of researchers such as Yanneke van der Ros, F. Gardiner and S. Salmenieme [9. 186 p].

Researchers have looked at various reasons for the low level of women's political activism. For example, one of the most common reasons for this is that political socialization directs men and women to different attitudes to different tasks, policies, and activities in general. Politics is an inconvenient area for women to expend their vital forces. The structural factors of participation in politics, that is, the factors related to the social structure of society are highlighted. Among them, the unequal distribution of resources that men and women can use in politics is highlighted. Inequality in education, income levels, and work experience, as a result of gender policies, leads to a shortage of women in the strata of society where they are recruited for politics, so they have fewer opportunities to participate in political life.

III. DISCUSSION

Women often come into politics from the fields of education and health, so they have less political experience than men. However, the situation has changed in recent years, with an increasing number of women lawyers and entrepreneurs with rich political experience. Situational and biographical factors were also considered. They are related to the characteristics of women's way of life in modern society. Most women are still responsible for running the household and raising children, so they do not have enough time or energy for political activity.

It is no coincidence that women enter politics at an older age than men, and that there are lonely, divorced, widowed, or childless people among the "women's political elite." It is devoted to the study of the experience of implementing the principle of gender equality in the political institutions of the world. This chapter examines the world experience in the formation of the system of state bodies and the implementation of the principle of gender equality in the activities of political parties, the types of quotas in the world, as well as the practice of effective use of certain quotas. It is noted that today there is a big difference between the countries of the world in the field of equal representation of both sexes in the executive branch.

The exact situation in each region can be justified differently. For example, the governments of Northern European countries have the largest number of women. This is primarily due to the fact that women themselves are extremely active in these countries. Therefore, measures have been introduced to support women at various levels of government. For example, the introduction of positive discrimination in the parliamentary elections allowed her, and therefore the country's government, to nominate many women candidates.

In Russia, researchers point out that the obstacle to women's appointment to political positions is that most appointments to high-level positions depend on top management, meaning that men are preferred at the time of appointment. Women make up more than 51% of the population of Uzbekistan, 25% of them are senators, 32% are women and 25% are deputies of local councils, 16 are in the Ministry of Internal Affairs, 7 are in the regional administration and more than 1,500 in other spheres. women have been participating in leadership positions. We cannot say that this still meets the demand in the total percentage [10.p.734-751].

Therefore, it is important to study scientifically and theoretically the issues related to ensuring the broad participation of women in socio-political life, creating all conditions for them to enter the socio-political process as an active force and develop ways to apply the results in practice.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A number of public policy demands that are currently on the agenda also apply directly to women. "In today's enlightened world," said President Mirziyoyev, "there is a special issue of women's interests, and it is no coincidence that great attention is paid to its study and solution." There is no need to talk at length about the future of such a society if women are not given enough attention».

A number of resolutions, decrees and orders developed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev urge to address the issue of "women" in terms of a new, national democratic development. In our opinion, the basis of this approach is the following views of the head of state [1.p.111]:

The first. "... The extent to which society has advanced on the path of democratic change, the attitude of this society towards women, determines its cultural and spiritual level."

The second. "... Raising the status and status of our dear mothers, sisters, wives and daughters in society, respecting them, protecting their interests, improving their working and living conditions should become a priority and the main goal of our state and society.

"Third." ... The main task of our state, government, local authorities, the general public should be to further enhance the role and status of our mothers, sisters, spouses, daughters in society, to restore their dignity, to alleviate their burden " [12. P.6898–6902].

It is clear from these fundamentally important ideas that social relations in Uzbekistan are built not on patriarchal, matriarchal, religious or communist approaches, but on the principle of "woman is great." This means that social relations are organized in the form of "subject-subject" and not "subject-object". It is known from historical development that the principle of "subject-object" has always been a priority in social relations.

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